

Notes

Synthesis and Characterisation of Lanthanone Complexes with Bis-(*o*-hydroxyacetophenone)-2,6-dipicolinoylidihydrazone

D. L. ARORA, KEEMTI LAL* and S. P. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, D. N. College, Meerut-250 002

Manuscript received 22 July 1985, accepted 25 June 1986

THE coordination chemistry of trivalent lanthanide ions has expanded rapidly during the last three decades. The majority of the complexes studied have been derived from strongly chelating anionic ligands with oxygen donor sites¹⁻³ and heterocyclic nitrogen containing ligands⁴⁻¹¹. In the present paper, we describe the synthesis and characterisation of the La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Ce^{IV} complexes with bis(*o*-hydroxyacetophenone)-2,6-dipicolinoylidihydrazone (hereafter adopted as adpH₄ or H₂L) and their characterisation by and elemental analyses, conductance, magnetic moment spectral studies.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and the solvents were purified before use.

Physical measurements: The metal contents were estimated either as metal oxides¹² or by complexometric titration by EDTA using xylenol orange as indicator¹³ at pH ~6. Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro combustion method, while C and H were determined at C.D R.I., Lucknow. Chloride ion was estimated as silver chloride. Other measurements were carried out as described earlier¹⁴.

Preparation of ligand: The ligand, bis(*o*-hydroxyacetophenone)-2,6-dipicolinoylidihydrazone (adpH₄ or H₂L) was synthesised as reported earlier¹⁴.

Preparation of complexes: The spec-pure oxides (B.A.R.C., Trombay) of lanthanides, La^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} were heated with excess of concentrated HCl to dryness. The metal chlorides so formed (0.002 M) were dissolved in ethanol (50%) and the ligand adpH₄ (0.001 M) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for about 4 h and then pH of the mixture was raised to ~7 and again digested for 2 h. The solid complexes so formed were filtered, washed successively with water and ethanol (50%) and dried under vacuum at room temperature

Results and Discussion

Analysis and properties of the metal chelates are given in Table 1.

Ir spectra: The ir frequencies together with their possible interpretation are described. The bands have been assigned by comparing the spectra of 2,6-dipicolinoylidihydrazine and its derivatives^{15,16}.

In the free ligand, pyridine ring vibrations as ν_{O-O} (pyridine ring breathing), ν_{O-N} (pyridine ring breathing, in-plane ring deformation and out-of-plane ring deformation) are observed at 1 595, 1 060, 640 and 420 cm⁻¹, respectively. These bands show an upward shift (10–30 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the complexes. These changes indicate pyridine–nitrogen coordination to metal ions^{17,18}. The medium bands appearing at 245–260 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{M-Py} vibrations^{17,18}.

The bands at 3 300, 1 670, 1 480, 1 290, 690 and 450 cm⁻¹ for adpH₄ are assigned to ν_{NH} , $\nu_{O=O}$ (amide-I), ($\nu_{ON} + \delta_{NH}$) (amide-II), ($\delta_{NH} + \nu_{CN}$) (amide-III), $\varphi_{O=O}$ (amide-IV) and $\pi_{O=O}$ (amide-VI) modes, respectively. The band at ~3 300 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicates that NH group remains intact during complexation. The bands for amide-II shows a downward shift (35–40 cm⁻¹) and the other

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS AND PROPERTIES OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd*	Colour	M.p. °C	Analyses % Found/(Calcd.)				Metal	Λ_M Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ_{eff} B.M.
			C	H	N	X			
[La ₂ LCI ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	Light yellow	290	31.27 (31.19)	2.52 (2.59)	7.81 (7.91)	16.11 (16.04)	30.93 (31.40)	91.0	Diamag.
[Ce ₂ LCI ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Brown	309	28.62 (28.80)	2.46 (2.40)	7.43 (7.30)	22.56 (22.22)	29.43 (29.24)	260.3	Diamag.
[Pr ₂ LCI ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	Yellow	295	31.17 (31.05)	2.62 (2.58)	7.71 (7.87)	15.86 (15.97)	31.10 (31.70)	75.4	3.1
[Nd ₂ LCI(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	Dark yellow	297	30.49 (30.82)	2.63 (2.56)	7.71 (7.81)	15.81 (15.86)	32.31 (32.22)	80.1	3.0
[Sm ₂ LCI ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	Yellow	310	30.72 (30.40)	2.49 (2.53)	7.64 (7.71)	15.51 (15.64)	33.24 (33.14)	85.0	1.3

* L = adpH₂ = C₂₀H₁₆N₂O₄. ^aDecomposed

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF THE COMPLEXES

Lanthanide ion	Level	Ln(NO ₃) ₃	[LnCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈]Cl	(1-β) × 10 ³	β	δ	b ^{1/2}
Pr	⁴ H ₄ → ¹ D ₂	16 980	16 850	0.756	0.992	0.76	0.061
	→ ³ P ₀	20 750	20 610				
	→ ³ P ₂	22 470	22 280				
Nd	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{5/2} , ³ H _{9/2}	12 470	12 300	0.757	0.992	0.76	0.061
	→ ⁴ F _{9/2}	14 640	14 520				
	→ ⁴ G _{5/2}	17 270	17 150				
	→ ⁴ G _{7/2}	19 460	19 300				
	→ ⁴ G _{9/2}	21 550	21 440				
Sm	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ I _{13/2}	21 550	21 440	0.496	0.995	0.050	0.050
	→ ⁴ P _{5/2}	24 000	23 880				
	→ ⁴ F _{9/2}	24 870	24 750				

Nitrate in aqueous solution, complexes in DMF.
L = adphH₄.

bands show an upward shift (10–25 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the complexes. These changes indicate coordination of secondary amide nitrogen atom to metal [—CONH(→M)—] (Refs. 15, 19, 20). A medium intensity band at 1 620 cm⁻¹ for the ligand is assigned to ν_{C-N} of the azomethine group. This band shows a downward shift (10–15 cm⁻¹) in the complexes, indicating the coordination of imino-nitrogen to the metal atom¹⁵. The bands appearing in the region 470–490 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{M-N}.

The bands at 3 360, 2 625, 1 550 and 1 260 cm⁻¹ for adphH₄ are assigned to ν_{OH} phenolic group, ν_{OH---N=C}, intra-molecular hydrogen bonding phenolic ν_{C-O} and δ_{C-O}, respectively²¹. In the complexes, the spectral bands due to ν_{OH} and ν_{OH---N=C} disappeared while other two shifted to upward frequencies (5–10 cm⁻¹) indicating metal and phenolic oxygen bonding. A weak band at ~530 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{M-O}. The band appearing in the region 3 380–3 390 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{OH} mode of coordinated water molecules in the complexes²¹. The band appearing at ~335 cm⁻¹ may be assigned ν_{M-O} vibrations in the complexes²¹.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra: The magnetic moments of the complexes (Table 1) are not in good agreement with those reported for typical lanthanide ions²². The low magnetic moments of these complexes can arise mainly due to the presence of antiferromagnetic interactions and lower symmetry components. Thus, it appears that these complexes possess a binuclear or polymeric structure, and strong metal–metal interactions take place between the two adjacent paramagnetic metal atoms, giving rise to low μ_{eff}.

The electronic spectra of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes have been taken in DMF and are recorded²³ in Table 2. The nephelauxetic parameter²⁴ (β), percentage covalency or Sinha's parameter (δ) and bonding parameter²⁵ (b^{1/2}) have been calculated (Table 2). The values indicate the extent of 4f-orbital participation in the complexation. Greater the magnitude of b^{1/2} greater is the contri-

bution of the 4f-orbital in complexation. The values of β are less than unity and values of δ and b^{1/2} are positive which indicate the covalency in the metal–ligand bond.

On the basis of the above discussion, it appears that the ligand acts as a heptadentate chelating agent having coordination sites at pyridine-nitrogen, two azomethine-nitrogen, two secondary amide-nitrogen and two phenolic-oxygen atoms. Both the lanthanides are in six-coordination environment, one lanthanide is present as LnN₃Cl₃ and the other as LnN₂O₄.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head of the Chemistry Department, Delhi University, for providing facilities.

References

1. T. MOELLER, D. F. MARTIN, L. C. THOMPSON, R. FERRUS, G. R. FEISTEL and W. J. RANDELL, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 1.
2. T. MOELLER, E. R. BIRNBAUM, J. H. FORSBERG, R. B. GAYHART, *Prog. Sci. Tech. Rare Earth*, 1968, 3, 66.
3. N. S. BIRADAR and V. B. MAHALE, *J. Less-Common Met.*, 1973, 31, 159.
4. F. A. HART and F. P. LAMING, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, 26, 579.
5. S. P. SINHA, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1964, 20, 879; *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 115; 1971, 33, 2205.
6. J. H. FORSBERG, T. M. KUBIK, T. MOELLER and K. GUCWA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 2656.
7. N. K. DUTT and S. RAHUT, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, 32, 2905.
8. N. K. DUTT and K. NAG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 2493, 2779.
9. E. BRUIHER and L. ZEKANY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 351.
10. M. MATLEY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 39, 491.
11. N. E. WULF and R. J. PRESSLEY, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 1963, 2, 152.
12. I. M. KOLTHOFF, P. J. ELVING and E. B. SANDELL, "Treatise on Analytical Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1963, Vol. 8, Part 2.
13. S. S. LYLE and M. M. RAHAMAN, *Talanta*, 1963, 10, 1177.
14. D. L. ARORA, K. LAL, S. P. GUPTA and S. K. SAHNI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1985, in the press.

- 15 S. K. SAHNI, S. P. GUPTA, S K SANGAL and V B RANA, *J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 200; *J Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 1048
- 16 V B RANA, S. K. SAHNI and S K SANGAL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 1498
- 17 D. A. BALDWIN, A B P LEVER and R. V. PARISH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 107
- 18 R. C. AGARWAL, N. K. SINGH and R. P. SINGH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, 20, 2794
- 19 M. NONOYAMA and K. YAMASAKI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 1969, 3, 385
- 20 M. NONOYAMA, S TOMITA and K. YAMASAKI, *Inorg. Chim Acta* 1975, 12, 33
- 21 K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970
- 22 B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, "Techniques of Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1965, Vol 4, p 137.
- 23 W. T. CARNALL, P. R. FIELDS and K. RAJNAH, *J Chem. Phys.*, 1968, 49, 4424.
- 24 C. K. JORGENSEN and B. R. JUDD, *Mol Phys.*, 1964, 8, 281.
- 25 D. E. HENRIE and G. R. CHOPPIN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 49, 477.

A Convenient Method for the Synthesis of Bis(isodicyclopentadienyl) Derivatives of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Titanium(IV) and Zirconium(IV)

R. K. SHARMA and C. P. SHARMA*

National Physical Laboratory, Hillside Road,
New Delhi-110 012

Manuscript received 20 January 1986, revised 5 May 1986,
accepted 18 June 1986

REINSCHNEIDER and Heymons¹ reported the synthesis of bis(isodicyclopentadienyl)iron(II) by the reaction of isodicyclopentadienyl magnesium bromide with iron(II) acetylacetonate. This was followed by the synthesis of thallium isodicyclopentadienide²⁻⁵ by treating an aqueous solution of thallium(I) sulphate with isodicyclopentadiene in the presence of sodium hydroxide. Thallium(I) isodicyclopentadiene is an extremely air-sensitive yellow compound and sublimes at 80° under reduced pressure (5×10^{-6} mm/Hg).

The present paper reports the synthesis of bis(isodicyclopentadienyl) derivatives of Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} by using thallium isodicyclopentadienide. All these compounds have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis and infrared studies.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was purified by distillation over sodium metal and lithium aluminium hydride. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by micro-analytical method, whereas metals estimated gravimetrically⁶.

Thallium isodicyclopentadienide was prepared by the reported method².

Bis(isodicyclopentadienyl)nickel(II): Nickel(II) bromide (2.2 g, 0.01 mol), tetrahydrofuran (100 ml) and thallium isodicyclopentadienide (6.7 g, 0.02 mol) were mixed and stirred for 6 h at room temperature and then filtered through a G-4 sintered glass frit. THF was removed under reduced pressure from the filtrate to give a brown coloured residue which on recrystallisation from n-pentane gave a red coloured crystalline compound (65%), m.p. 165° d.

Bis(isodicyclopentadienyl)cobalt(II), **bis(isodicyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride** and **bis(isodicyclopentadienyl)zirconium(IV) dichloride** were prepared by the similar procedure, except that their recrystallisation from pentane was done at -25°.

Analytical data for these compounds are given in Table 1. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 137 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	Yield %	Analysis % : ound/(Calcd)			
			C	H	Metal	Cl
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁) ₂ Ni	165	65	74.72 (74.85)	6.62 (6.86)	18.58 (18.31)	-
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁) ₂ Co	172	64	74.86 (74.85)	6.67 (6.86)	18.45 (18.37)	-
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁) ₂ TiCl ₂	235	70	62.84 (63.02)	5.50 (5.78)	12.18 (12.57)	18.42 (18.62)
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁) ₂ ZrCl ₂	250	65	56.01 (56.85)	4.92 (5.19)	20.80 (21.51)	16.48 (16.71)

Results and Discussions

The formation of the bis-isodicyclopentadienyl complexes could be represented as

All the complexes were stable in inert and dry atmosphere, and more soluble in polar organic solvents than in the non-polar solvents. Cobalt(II) derivative oxidised in air to the corresponding cobalt(III) derivatives after prolonged standing in dry air. Titanium and zirconium derivatives were very sensitive to moisture.

Infrared spectra: All the compounds show medium to very strong ir bands in the regions 3050-100, 2980-950, 1560-540, 1440-445, 1410-400 cm⁻¹, which correspond to 3 050-100 cm⁻¹ and 2 980-950 cm⁻¹ $\nu_{\sigma-H}$, $\nu_{\sigma-C}$ 1 560-540 cm⁻¹ δ_{CH_2} 1 410-400 cm⁻¹ vibrations⁷, respectively. The two